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REMOTE MONITORING L.V. SWITCHBOARD POWER STATUS WITH 5G NEW RADIO NETWORK APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

In a power distribution system of most of the buildings, A Low Voltage (L.V.) switchboard was applied to protect the system. There are different components in the switchboard (e.g. circuit breakers, over current protection relay, earth fault protection relay etc.). There are also some components for measure the power quality which is the power analyser. A power analyser (including Voltmeter, Ammeter, Multi-meter) is using to measure the power quality in the electrical power distribution system. Most of the electrical power distributions systems have been connected the power analysers to a building management system. The power analysers connected to a computer in a fixed position that means if someone wants to check the power distribution status, the person needs to go to the computer to check. In this project, a system would be made to monitoring the power status by 5G New Radio (NR) Network application with android smartphone. Since 5G NR Network can provide a theoretical peak download capacity of 20 Gigabits per second. It would be more convenient to monitoring the power status in different place by checking though in the Internet of Things (IoT) .

KEYWORDS

Low Voltage (L.V.) switchboard, 5G New Radio (NR) Network, Internet of Things, Mobile Network.

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SMART MOTORCYCLE HELMET: REAL-TIME CRASH DETECTION WITH EMERGENCY NOTIFICATION, TRACKER AND ANTI-THEFT SYSTEM USING INTERNET-OF-THINGS CLOUD BASED TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Buying a car entails a cost, not counting the day to day high price tag of gasoline. People are looking for viable means of transportation that is cost-effective and can move its way through traffic faster. In the Philippines, motorcycle was the answer to most people transportation needs. With the increasing number of a motorcycle rider in the Philippines safety is the utmost concern. Today technology plays a huge role on how this safety can be assured. We now see advances in connected devices. Devices can sense its surrounding through sensor attach to it. With this in mind, this study focuses on the development of a wearable device named Smart Motorcycle Helmet or simply Smart Helmet, whose main objective is to help motorcycle rider in times of emergency. Utilizing sensors such as alcohol level detector, crash/impact sensor, Internet connection thru 3G, accelerometer, Short Message Service (SMS) and cloud computing infrastructure connected to a Raspberry Pi Zero-W and integrating a separate Arduino board for the anti-theft tracking module is used to develop the propose Internet-of Things (IoT) device.

Using quantitative method and descriptive type research, the researchers validated the results from the inputs of the participant who tested the smart helmet during the alpha and beta testing process. Taking into account the ethical consideration of the volunteers, who will test the Smart Helmet. To ensure the reliability of the beta and alpha testing, ISO 25010 quality model was used for the assessment focusing on the device accuracy, efficiency and functionality. Based on the inputs and results gathered, the proposed Smart Helmet IoT device can be used as a tool in helping a motorcycle rider when an accident happens to inform the first-responder of the accident location and informing the family of the motorcycle rider.

KEYWORDS

Smart Helmet, Internet of Things, Sensors, Real-Time Crash Detection, Emergency Notification, Tracker, Anti-Theft System Cloud Based Technology

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